

Search for Potent Anthelmintics. Part IV. 2-(Benzimidazolymethylthio)-3-Aryl or Cyclohexyl-4- Quinazolones and N-(4-Quinazolone-2-ylmercaptoacetyl) Hydrazones

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A series of 2-(2-benzimidazolymethylthio)-3-aryl-4-quinazolones and N-(3-aryl-4-quinazolone-2-ylmercaptoacetyl) hydrazones has been synthesised as potential anthelmintic agents.

QUINAZOLINE derivatives^{1,2}, 2-substituted benzimidazoles³, isocyanates⁴, isothiocyanates⁵ and anthranilic acid derivatives⁷ include some of the most effective and best tolerated anthelmintics reported so far. Sen and coworkers⁸ have shown that derivatives of benzoxazinedione (I) possess cestocidal activity.

In view of this structural analogy, it was considered of worth to synthesise 2-(2-benzimidazolymethylthio)-3-aryl or cyclohexyl-4-quinazolones (II) incorporating -NCO group in cyclic structure and a thiomethylene (-S-CH₂-) bridge between benzimidazole and quinazolone moieties. The pronounced anthelmintic activity exhibited by several hydrazines⁹

It is evident from above that 2-mercapto-3-aryl-4-quinazolone (II), a condensation product of anthranilic acid and aryl isothiocyanate, bears a close structural resemblance to the active benzoxazinedione derivative (I).

and hydrazones¹⁰ also gave us impetus to undertake the synthesis of N-(3-Aryl-4-quinazolone-2-ylmercaptoacetyl) hydrazones (IV) with a view to ascertaining whether the presence of quinazolone nucleus can induce anthelmintic activity in these compounds.

2-Mercapto-3-aryl-4-quinazolones (II), obtained by condensing anthranilic acid with appropriate aryl isothiocyanates, on interaction with 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole in the presence of alcoholic NaOH furnished 2-(2-benzimidazolymethylthio)-3-aryl-4-quinazolones (III).

Treatment of (II) with ethylchloroacetate in the presence of alcoholic NaOH at room temperature also yielded 2-(ethoxycarbonylmethylthio)-3-aryl-4-quinazolones. The latter were condensed with hydrazine hydrate to get N-(3-Aryl-4-quinazolone-2-ylmercaptoacetyl) hydrazines which on refluxing with aldehydes or ketones in absolute ethanol produced the hydrazones (IV).

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected.

at room temperature. The reaction mixture after being kept overnight was refluxed for 1 hr. On cooling a solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with a little water and recrystallised from dil. ethanol or dioxane. The yield of the product varied between 40 to 50%. The melting points and elemental analysis of prepared compounds are recorded in table 1.

2-(Ethoxycarbonylmethylthio)-3-aryl-4-quinazolones : These were prepared by the method adopted earlier¹⁴.
N-(3-Aryl-4-quinazolone-2-ylmercaptoacetyl) hydrazines :

2-(Ethoxycarbonylmethylthio)-3-aryl-4-quinazolone (0.01 mole), hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mole) and absolute alcohol (25 ml) were mixed in a 100 ml r. b. flask and the mixture refluxed for 8 hrs on a steam bath. The solvent was distilled off under reduced pressure. The residue was washed with small portions of cold water. Recrystallisation was

TABLE 1. 2-(2-BENZIMIDAZOLYLMETHYLTHIO)-3-ARYL OR CYCLOHEXYL-4-QUINAZOLONES (III)

S. N.	R	X	m.p. °C	Molecular Formula	Found	% of N Calculated
1.	Phenyl	H	145-47	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ OS	14.32	14.58
2.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	210	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ ClN ₄ OS	13.21	13.38
3.	α -Naphthyl	H	254	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ OS	13.01	12.90
4.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	H	230-34	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ BrN ₄ OS	12.04	12.09
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	196	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ OS	13.90	14.07
6.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	H	232	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ OS	13.88	14.07
7.	Cyclohexyl	H	262	C ₂₃ H ₂₂ N ₄ OS	14.51	14.35
8.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	H	200-3	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S	13.78	13.52
9.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	5-Cl	215-16	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ OS	12.82	12.94
10.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	5-Cl	189	C ₂₃ H ₁₄ Cl ₂ N ₄ OS	12.46	12.36
11.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	5-Cl	245	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ OS	12.90	12.94
12.	Phenyl	5-Cl	210-12	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₄ OS	13.54	13.38
13.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	5-Cl	230-32	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	12.52	12.48

2-Mercapto-3-aryl-4-quinazolones (II) : These were synthesised from anthranilic acid and arylisothiocyanate by a published procedure¹¹. The required isothiocyanates were prepared by the method described by Vogel¹².

2-Chloromethylbenzimidazoles : were prepared according to a reported procedure¹³.

2-(2-Benzimidazolymethylthio)-3-aryl or cyclohexyl-4-quinazolones (III).

In a 100 ml r. b. flask, 3-aryl-2-mercapto-4-quinazolone (0.01 mole) was dissolved in a minimum volume of 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution. To this solution 2-chloromethylbenzimidazole (0.01 mole) dissolved in a minimum quantity of alcohol was added dropwise from a dropping funnel with stirring. The stirring was further continued for 2 hrs.

effected from ethanol. The yield varied between 50 to 60%. Analysis and melting points of compounds obtained are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2. N-(3-ARYL-4-QUINAZOLON-2-YLMERCAPTOACETYL)-HYDRAZINES

S. N.	Ar.	m.p. °C	Molecular formula	% of N Found	Calculated
1.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	190-92	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.61	16.47
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	145	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S	16.54	16.47
3.	Phenyl	140	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S	17.32	17.18

N-(3-Aryl-4-quinazolone-2-ylmercaptoacetyl) hydrazones (IV) :

A mixture of N-(3-Aryl-4-quinazolone-2-ylmercaptoacetyl) hydrazine (0.01 mole), aldehyde or ketone (0.01 mole) and absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed on a steam bath for 8 hrs. The solvent was distilled

TABLE 3. N-(3-ARYL-4-QUINAZOLON-2-YLMERCAPTOACETYL) HYDRAZONES (IV)

S. N.	Ar.	R ₁	R ₂	m.p. °C	Molecular Formula	% of N	
						Found	Calculated
1.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	203	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	12.14	12.11
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Phenyl	CH ₃	208	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ S	12.42	12.67
3.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Phenyl	CH ₃	222	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ S	12.71	12.67
4.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	H	215	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃ S	12.58	12.61
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	224-25	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	12.01	12.11
6.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Phenyl	H	206-7	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	12.84	13.08
7.	Phenyl	Phenyl	H	207-8	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₂ S	13.31	13.52
8.	Phenyl	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	210	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ ClN ₄ O ₂ S	12.24	12.48
9.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	H	228-30	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	12.60	12.61
10.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Phenyl	H	198-200	C ₂₄ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	13.12	13.08
11.	Phenyl	<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	H	240	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃ S	13.41	13.02
12.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	2-Furyl	H	210-13	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₃ S	13.51	13.39

off and the residue recrystallised from alcohol or dilute acetic acid. The yield varied between 40 to 50%. The analytical data of the compounds thus prepared are reported in Table 3.

The results of pharmacological screening of these compounds will be published elsewhere.

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